

**International Journal of
Management Focus**

ISSN 2277 – 5684

IJMF

www.ijmf.in

SEPTEMBER 2015 - VOLUME 5 ISSUE 3

**Archers
& Elevators Publishing House**

www.aeph.in | archerselevators@gmail.com

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SUPERVISORY STRATEGIES TO SURMOUNT STRESS

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INTRODUCTION

Supervisory stress starts with identifying the source of stress in your life. This isn't as easy as it sounds. Your true sources of stress aren't always obvious, and it's all too easy to overlook your own stress-inducing thoughts, feelings, and behaviours. Sure, you may know that you're constantly worried about work deadlines. But maybe it's your procrastination, rather than the actual job demands, that leads to deadline stress.

TO IDENTIFY YOUR TRUE SOURCES OF STRESS, LOOK CLOSELY AT YOUR HABITS, ATTITUDES AND EXCUSES:

- Do you explain away stress as temporary
- ("I just have a million things going on right now") even though you can't remember the last time you took a breather?
- Do you define stress as an integral part of your work or home life
- ("Things are always crazy around here") or as a part of your personality ("I have a lot of nervous energy, that's all")
- Do you blame your stress on other people or outside events, or view it as entirely normal and unexceptional?

Until you accept responsibility for the role you play in creating or maintaining it, your stress level will remain outside your control.

It may seem that there's nothing you can do about your stress level. The bills aren't going to stop coming, there will never be more hours in the day for all your errands, and your career or family responsibilities will always be demanding. But you have a lot more control than you might think. In fact, the simple realization that you're in control of your life is the foundation of supervisory stress.

INDIVIDUAL COPING STRATEGIES

Managing stress is all about taking charge your thoughts, emotions, schedule, environment, and the way you deal with problems. The ultimate goal is a balanced life, with time for work, relationship, relaxation and fun-plus the resilience to hold up under pressure and meet challenges head on. A stress note can help you identify the regular stressors in your life and the way you deal with them. Each time you feel stressed, keep track of it in your dairy, as you keep a daily log, you will begin to see patterns and common themes.

- What caused your stress (make a guess if you're unsure)
- How you felt, both physically and emotionally.
- How you acted in response.
- What you did to make yourself feel better.

Currently cope with individual stress

Think about the ways you currently manage and cope with stress in your life .your stress diary can help you to identify them. Are your coping strategies healthy or unhealthy, helpful or unproductive? Unfortunately, many people cope with stress in ways that compound the problem.

Detrimental ways of coping with individual stress

These coping strategies may temporarily reduce stress, but they cause more damage in the long run;

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Smoking ➤ Ingestion too much ➤ In excess of eating or under eating ➤ Zoning out for hours in front of the TV or computer ➤ Moving back from friends, family and activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Using drugs to relax ➤ Resting too much ➤ Procrastinating ➤ Filling up every minute of the day to avoid facing tribulations ➤ Enchanting out of your stress on others (lashing out , angry outbursts, physical violence)
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LEARNING BETTER WAYS TO MANAGE INDIVIDUAL STRESS

If your methods of coping with stress aren't contributing to your greater emotional and physical health, it's time to find healthier ones. There are many healthy ways to manage and cope with stress, but they all require to change. You can either change the situation or change your reaction. When deciding which option to choose, it's helpful to think of the **FOUR C'S**.

Since everyone has a unique response to stress, there is no "one size fits all" solution to managing it. No single method works for everyone or in every situation, so experiment with different techniques and strategies. Focus on what makes you feel calm and in control.

Dealing with stressful situation: The four C's

<p>Change the circumstances:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Circumvent the stressor ➤ Change the stressor 	<p>Change your comeback</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Carbon copy yourself to the stressor ➤ Confess the stressor.
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SUPERVISORY STRESS TACTICS BY USING 4 C'S

- Circumvent unnecessary stress
- Not all stress can be avoided, and it's not healthy to avoid a situation that need to be addressed. You may be surprised, however, by the number of stressors in your life that you can eliminate.

- Learn how to say "no" - know your limits and stick to them. Whether in your personal or professional life, refuse to accept added responsibility when you're close to reaching them. Taking on more than you can handle is a surefire recipe for stress.
- Avoid people who stress you out-If someone consistently causes stress in your life and you can't turn the relationship around, limit the amount of time you spend with that person or end the relationship entirely.
- Take control of your environment-If the evening news makes you anxious, turn the TV off. If traffic's got you tense, take a longer but less-traveled route. If going to the market is an unpleasant chore, do your grocery shopping online.
- Pare down your to-do list-Analyze your schedule, responsibilities and daily tasks. If you've got too much on your plate, distinguish between the "should" and the "musts". Drop tasks that aren't truly necessary to the bottom of the list or eliminate them entirely.
- Change the situation
- If you can't avoid a stressful situation, try to alter it. Figure out what you can do to change things so the problem doesn't present itself in the future. Often, this involves changing the way you communicate and operate in your daily life.
- Express your feelings instead of bottling them up. If something or someone is bothering you, communicate your concerns in an open and respectful way. If you don't voice your feelings, resentment will build and the situation will likely remain the same.
- Be willing to compromise. When you ask someone to change their behavior, be willing to do the same. If you both are willing to bend at least a little, you'll have a good chance of finding a happy middle ground.
- Be more assertive. Don't take backseat in your own life. Deal with problems head on, doing your best to anticipate and prevent them. If you've got an exam to study for and your chatty roommate just got home, say up front that you only have five minutes to talk.
- Manage your time better. Poor time management can cause a lot of stress. When you're stretched too thin and running behind, it's hard to stay calm and focused. But if you plan ahead and make sure you don't overextend yourself, you can alter the amount of stress you're under.
- Carbon copy to the stressor
- If you can't change the stressor, change yourself. You can adapt to stressful situations and regain your sense of control by changing your expectations and attitude.
- Reframe problems. Try to view stressful situations from a more positive perspective. Rather than fuming about a traffic jam, look at it as an opportunity to pause and regroup, listen to your favourite radio station or enjoy some alone time.
- Look at the big picture. Take perspective of the stressful situation. Ask yourself how important it will be in the long run. Will it matter in a month? A year? Is it really worth getting upset over? If the answer is no, focus your time and energy elsewhere.
- Adjust your standards .Perfectionism is a major source of avoidable stress. Stop setting yourself up for failure by demanding perfection. Set reasonable standards for yourself and others and learn to be okay with "good enough".

- Focus on the positive .when stress is getting you down, take a moment to reflect on all things you appreciate in your life, including your own positive qualities and gifts. This simple strategy can help you keep things in perspective.
- Confess the things you can't change
- Some sources of stress are unavoidable. You can't prevent or change stressors such as the death of a loved one, a serious illness, or a national recession. In such cases, the best way to cope with stress is to accept things as they are. Acceptance may be difficult, but in the long run, it's easier than railing against a situation you can't change.
- Don't try to control the uncontrollable. Many things in life are beyond our control - particularly the behavior of other people. Rather than stressing out over them, focus on the things you can control such as the way you choose to react to problems.
- Look for the upside. As the saying goes, "what doesn't kill us makes us stronger." When facing major challenges, try to look at them as opportunities for personal growth. If your own poor choices contributed to a stressful situations, reflect on them and learn from your mistakes.
- Share your feelings. Talk to a trusted friend or make an appointment with a therapist. Expressing what you're going through can be very cathartic, even if there's nothing you can do to alter the stressful situation.
- Learn to forgive. Accept the fact that we live in an imperfect world and that people make mistakes. Let go of anger and resentments. Free yourself from negative energy by forgiving and moving on.

II) ORGANISATIONAL COPING STRATEGIES.

In this difficult economy, many of us are finding it harder than ever to cope with stress in the workplace. Regardless of occupation, seniority, or salary level, we're spending more and more of our work days feeling frazzled and out control, instead of alert and relaxed.

While some stress is a normal part of the workplace, excessive stress can interfere with your productivity and reduce your physical and emotional health. Finding ways to manage workplace stress is not about making huge changes to every aspect of our work life or rethinking career ambitions. Rather, stress management requires focus on the one thing that's always within your control.

Coping with work stress in today's uncertain climate

For workers everywhere, the troubled economy may feel like an emotional roller coaster. "Lays off" and "budget cuts" have become by words in the workplace, and the result is increased fear, uncertainty and higher levels of stress.

Since job and workplace stress increase in times of economic crisis, it's important to learn new and better ways of coping with the pressure.

The ability to manage in the workplace can not only improve your physical and emotional health, it can also make the difference between success and Failure on the job. Your emotions are contagious and stress has an impact on the quality of your interactions with others. The better you are at managing your own stress, the more you'll positively affect those around you and the less other people's stress will negatively affect you

Scan how to manage job stress.

There are a variety of steps you can take to reduce both your overall stress levels and the stress you find on the job and in the workplace.

These include:

- Captivating task for improving your physical and touching well-being
- Pass up pitfalls by identifying hasty habits and harmful approaches that add to the stress you experience at work.
- Facts improved communication skills to ease and improve your relationships with management and coworkers.

TIPS TO AVOID UNNECESSARY STRESS IN WORKPLACE

- Identify caution signs of unnecessary stressed at work
- When you feel overwhelmed at work, you lose confidence and may become irritable or withdrawn. This can make you less productive and less effective in your job and make the work seem less rewarding. If you ignore the waning sign of work stress, they can lead to bigger problems. Beyond interfering with job performance and satisfaction, chronic or intense stress can also lead to physical and emotional health problems.

Indicators of extreme job and workplace stress

➤ Feeling anxious, irritable, or depressed	➤ Muscle tension or headaches
➤ Apathy, loss of interest in work	➤ Stomach problems
➤ Problems sleeping	➤ Social withdrawal
➤ Fatigue	➤ Loss of sex drive
➤ Trouble concentrating	➤ Using alcohol or drugs to cope

Common causes of excessive workplace stress

- Fear of being laid off
- More overtime due to staff cutbacks
- Pressure to perform to meet rising expectations but with no increases in job satisfaction
- Pressure to work at optimum levels-all the time!
- Shrink work stress by taking care of yourself
- When stress at work interface with your ability to perform in your job, manage your personal life, or adversely impacts your health, it's time to take action. Start by paying attention to your physical and emotional health .when your own needs is taken care of, you're stronger and more resilient to stress. The better you feel, the better equipped you'll be to manage work stress without becoming overwhelmed.
- Taking care of you doesn't require a total lifestyle overhaul. Even small things can lift your mood, increase your energy and make you feel like you're back in the driver's seat. Take things one step at a time and as you make more positive lifestyle choices, you'll soon notice a reduction in your stress levels, both at home and at work.

Make food choices that keep you going

Low Blood sugar can make you feel anxious and irritable, while eating too much can make you lethargic .By eating small but frequent meals throughout the day, you can help

your body maintain an even level of blood sugar and avoid these swings in mood. To learn more about food that can have a calming effect, lift your mood and make you feel good.

Drink alcohol in moderation and avoid nicotine

Alcohol temporarily reduces anxiety and worry, but too much can cause anxiety as it wears off. Drinking to relieve job stress may also eventually lead to alcohol abuse and dependence. Similarly, smoking when you're feeling stressed and overwhelmed may seem calming, but nicotine is a powerful stimulant-leading to higher, not lower, levels of anxiety.

Get enough sleep

Not only can stress and worry can cause insomnia, but a lack of sleep can leave you vulnerable to even more stress. When you're well-rested, it's much easier to keep your emotional balance, a key factor in coping with job and workplace stress.

III) CONDENSE JOB STRESS BY PRIORITIZING AND CATEGORIZING

When job and workplace stress threatens to overwhelm you, there are simple steps you can take to regain control over yourself and the situation. Your newfound ability to maintain a sense of self-control in stressful situations will often be well-received by coworkers, managers and subordinates alike, which can lead to better relationship at work. Here are some suggestions for reducing job stress by prioritizing and organizing your responsibilities.

Time management tips for dropping job stress

- **Create a balanced schedule:** Analyze your schedule, responsibilities, and daily tasks. All work and no play is a recipe for burnout. Try to find a balance between work and family life, social activities and solitary pursuits, daily responsibilities and downtime.
- **Don't over-commit yourself:** Avoid scheduling things back-to-back or trying to fit too much into one day. All too often we underestimate how long things will take. If you've got too much on your plate, distinguish between the "should" and the "musts". Drop tasks that aren't truly necessary to the bottom of the list or eliminate them entirely.
- **Try to leave earlier in the morning:** Even 10-15 minutes can make the difference between frantically rushing to your desk and having time to ease into your day. Don't add to your stress levels by running late.
- **Plan regular breaks:** Make sure to take short breaks throughout the day to take a walk or sit back and clear your mind. Also try to get away from your desk or work station for lunch. Stepping away from work to briefly relax and recharge will help you be more, not less, productive.

Task management tips for falling job stress:

- **Prioritize tasks:** Make a list of tasks you have to do and tackle them in order of importance. Do the high-priority items first. If you have something particularly unpleasant to do, get it over with early. The rest of your day will be more pleasant as a result.
- **Break projects into small steps:** If a large project seems overwhelming, make a step-by-step plan. Focus on one manageable step at a time, rather than taking on everything at once.

- **Delegate responsibility:** You don't have to do it all yourself. If other people can take care of the task, why not let them? Let go the desire to control every little step. You'll be letting go of unnecessary stress in the process.
- **Be willing to compromise:** When you ask someone to contribute differently to a task, revise a deadline or change their behavior at work, be willing to do the same. Sometimes, if you can both bend a little, you'll be able to find a happy middle ground that reduces the stress levels for everyone concerned.
- Decrease job stress by improving exciting brainpower
- Even if you're in a job where the environment has grown increasingly stressful, you can retain a large measure of self-control and self-confidence by understanding and practicing emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is about communicating with others in ways that draw people to you, overcome differences, repair wounded feelings and defuse tension and stress.

Exciting brainpower in the work place has four major components:

- **Person awareness-** The ability to recognize your emotions and their impact while using gut feeling to guide your decisions
- **Individual management-** The ability to control your emotions and behavior and adapt to changing circumstances
- **Public awareness-** The ability to sense, understands and reacts to other's emotions and feels comfortable socially.
- **Rapport management-** The ability to inspire, influences and connects to others and manages conflict.
- Ease job stress by breaking bad habits:
- As you learn to manage your stress and improve your work relationships, you will have more control over your ability to think clearly and act appropriately. You will be able to break habits that add to your stress at work-and you'll even be able to change negative ways of thinking about things that only add to your stress.

FOUR WAYS TO DISPEL STRESS

- **Take time away:** when stress is mounting at work, try to take a quick break and move away from the stressful situation. Take a stroll outside the workplace if possible, or spend a few minute mediating in the break room. Physical movements or finding a quiet place to regain your balance can quickly reduce stress.
- **Talk it over with someone:** In some situations, simply sharing your thoughts and feeling with someone you trust can help reduce stress. Talking over a problem with someone who is both supportive and empathetic can be a great way to let off steam and relive stress
- **Connect with other at work:** developing friendship with some of your co-workers can help buffer you from the negative effects of stress. Remember to listen to them and offer support when they are in need as well.
- **Look for humour in the situation:** when used appropriately, humour is a great way to diffuse stress in the workplace. When you or those around you start taking things too seriously, find a way to lighten the mood by sharing a joke or funny story.

CONCLUSION:

It is vital that supervisory stress techniques are implemented into our everyday lives. As mentioned earlier, some stress is good, but we need to find that optimal level of stress, which will motivate but not overwhelm us. Coping with stress is an individualized task and one method over another may not be superior, so find what work for you and master it. A person that is stressed takes so much away from his or her health and performance levels. Reducing stress could be as simple as adding exercise to your day or making new friends. To make the most of your life, limit your stress and of course for that stress that you cannot diminish, learn to manage it. Take a walk, go dancing, stretch, take deep breathes, laugh, play a game, see a movie, express affection, share feelings, sing, paint, write, make new friends, tackle problems head on, give thanks, let go, and laugh some more...

It's a manager's best interest to keep stress levels in the workplace to a minimum. Managers can act as positive role models, especially in times of high stress, by following the tips outlined in this article. If a respected manager can remain calm in stressful work situations, it is much easier for his or her employees to also remain calm.

Additionally, there are a number of organizational changes that managers and employers can make to reduce workplace stress like improve communication, consult the employees, cultivate a friendly social climate etc...

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